

IPBES TCA Chapter 3. Review of knowledge on theories and frameworks of transformative change / IPBES transformative change assessment

List of references selected on theories and frameworks of transformative change

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Pervasive human-driven decline of life on Earth points to the need for transformative change, Science Vol 366, No 6471 (13 December 2019) SANDRA DÍAZ; JOSEF SETTELE; EDUARDO S. BRONDÍZIO; HIEN T. NGO, JOHN AGARD; ALMUT ARNETH, PATRICIA BALVANERA; KATE A. BRAUMAN; STUART H. M. BUTCHART, [...], AND CYNTHIA N. ZAYAS